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Aspects of the Polish Staff of the Commander-in-Chief's Relations with the British War Office: Planning for the Post-War Polish Army, 1943-1945*

Relacje Sztabu Naczelnego Wodza z brytyjskim Ministerstwem Wojny w latach 1943-1945 w zakresie planowania rozbudowy powojennego Wojska Polskiego

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Abstract: This paper considers the creation of plans for the expansion and development of the Polish land forces in the post-World War II period, which were carried out between 1941 and 1944 at the General Staff of the Polish Armed Forces. The future development of the Polish Army included both the use of units under Allied operational command and the recruitment of several hundred thousand Poles either interned or imprisoned in France, Switzerland, Germany, Hungary and Romania. Finally, the so-called Plan 'P' anticipated the expansion of the ground forces to a level of more than 470,000 troops. The article also refers to the sceptical approach of the British authorities to the possibility of implementing the mentioned plan, until the final rejection of the Polish concept in the autumn of 1944. In addition, the article makes a brief comparison between the planned personnel development of the Polish Armed Forces in the West and the People's Army of Poland (which consisted of 400,000 soldiers in 1945 and only 147,000 in 1947), pointing out that the personnel level of Plan 'P' would most probably be impossible to maintain in post-war conditions.

Keywords: World War II, Staff of the Commander-in-Chief, Polish Armed Forces in the West, planning the development of the armed forces

Streszczenie: Niniejszy artykuł omawia kwestie opracowywania w latach 1941-1944 w Sztabie Naczelnego Wodza Polskich Sił Zbrojnych planów rozbudowy i rozwoju wojsk lądowych w okresie po zakończeniu II wojny światowej. Przyszły rozwój Wojska Polskiego uwzględniał zarówno wykorzystanie jednostek znajdujących się pod operacyjnym dowództwem Aliantów, jak również wcielenie kilkuset tysięcy Polaków internowanych lub więzionych na terenie Francji, Szwajcarii, Niemiec, Węgier i Rumunii. Ostatecznie tzw. Plan „P” uwzględniał rozbudowę wojsk lądowych do poziomu ponad 470 tys. żołnierzy. W artykule poruszono także kwestię sceptycznego podejścia władz brytyjskich do możliwości realizacji ww. planu, aż do ostatecznego odrzucenia polskiej koncepcji jesienią 1944 roku. Dodatkowo w artykule dokonano pobieżnego porównania planowanego rozwoju osobowego Polskich Sił Zbrojnych na Zachodzie z ludowym Wojskiem Polskim (liczącego w 1945 roku 400 tys. żołnierzy, ale w 1947 roku już tylko 147 tys.), wskazując, że poziom sił Planu „P” byłby najprawdopodobniej nie do utrzymania w warunkach powojennych.

Słowa kluczowe: II wojna światowa, Sztab Naczelnego Wodza, Polskie Siły Zbrojne na Zachodzie, planowanie rozwoju sił zbrojnych

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During the Second World War, the Polish land forces in the West were closely integrated organizationally and operationally with those of their British counterparts. The high levels of integration attained by the Polish armed forces in many important aspects, including doctrine, organization and equipment, were comparable to those enjoyed by Commonwealth forces during the war. One of the key factors that made this integration possible was the relationship between the Staff of the Commander-in-Chief (*Sztab Naczelnego Wodza*) of the Polish Armed Forces in London and the British War Office. In this paper the Staff of the Commander-in-Chief of the Polish Armed Forces will be referred to as the Polish General Staff. From the time of its establishment in 1940 at the Hotel Rubens in London, the Polish General Staff developed a working relationship with the War Office in Whitehall that dealt with a full range of issues necessary for the preparation and employment of Polish forces within the British war effort. While it is not the intention here to examine the full spectrum of interaction between the Polish General Staff and the British War Office, one particularly crucial issue that emerged in 1943, concerned planning for the future development of Polish land forces. This was an issue that had its wartime and post-war implications. This paper will therefore examine the Polish General Staff's Plans for the post-war Polish Army and the War Office reaction to the Polish plans, and will conclude with an assessment of the third phase of the General Staff's vision for the post-war Polish Army.

THE POLISH GENERAL STAFF'S PLAN FOR THE POST-WAR POLISH ARMY

The Polish General Staff in London had engaged in some preliminary study in 1941-42 on the development of Polish land forces after the war. The papers drafted set out assumptions and factors regarding the future Polish Army and explored several variants of a force structure.¹ The work was analytical rather than producing a coherent plan for force development. The prompt for a more practical plan came at the instigation of the British War Office. Lieutenant General Sir Arthur Edward Grasett, who from December 1942 was responsible for dealing with Allied Forces, requested information in the course of the summer of 1943 from the Polish General Staff on future plans for developing the Polish Army.²

The work in producing a plan for the development of Polish land forces rested in two branches of the General Staff: Planning and Organization. Lieutenant Colonel Ignacy Banach headed the Planning Branch (*Oddział Planowania*) in the period that the three-phase plan was generated. He was an officer of wide

¹ Polish Institute and Sikorski Museum (hereafter PISM), London, Akta Komisji Studiów: organizacja Sił Zbrojnych w przyszłości, A.XII.22-131e.

² PISM, Letter General S. Kopański to Lt. General A.S. Grasett, 4 December 1943, A.XII.26-81.

staff experience, particularly in intelligence.³ Heading the Organizational Branch (*Oddział Organizacyjny*) was Lieutenant Colonel Wielisław Krajowski. He held this post in London throughout most of the war.⁴ From surviving records, the division of labour between the two branches suggests that the Planning Branch was responsible for the overall design of the plan while the Organizational Branch oversaw the detailed requirements, particularly for the wartime aspects of the plan.⁵

The Polish General Staff produced a plan that General Stanisław Kopański, Chief of the Polish General Staff, forwarded to General Grasett on 4 December 1943. Called the Plan 'P' by the General Staff, it envisaged the development of the Polish land forces in three phases (see Annex A for the full text). A key element underpinning the plan in each phase was the ability to access Polish manpower to allow expansion of the army to take place. In the first phase, the liberation of France and access to Switzerland meant gaining as many as 500,000 men in France and over 10,000 Polish soldiers of the 2nd Polish Infantry Division (*Druga Dywizja Strzelców Pieszych – 2 DSP*) interned since 1940 in Switzerland. In the second phase, Polish manpower found in Germany, Hungary and Romania would provide the basis of expansion. In Germany, Poles working as forced labour, forced into military service in the German armed forces, and Polish prisoners of war held since 1939, amounted in Polish General Staff estimates to a manpower pool of over 1.2 million. Hungary and Romania together would yield small numbers of manpower in comparison to that of Germany. The final third phase anticipated drawing on manpower reserves in liberated Poland and provided the greatest opportunity for military expansion. The large pool consisting of untrained age groups eligible for military service was the key to expansion in this phase. Trained military manpower in Poland was estimated at only 160,000.⁶ Drawing on the additional manpower calculated to be available in each phase of the plan, Polish land forces would be progressively expanded and their capabilities developed.

The first wartime phase focussed on bringing up to strength operational formations, building a pool of replacements and filling cadre formations in anticipation of making them operational. At the end of the first phase of the plan, Polish land forces in the West would consist of an army headquarters, two corps headquarters (with corps troops), two armoured divisions, a parachute brigade, and a tank brigade. The second phase was to occur in the immediate post-war period. The anticipated growth in the force structure would see the number of corps headquarters increase

³ *Banach, Ignacy Kazimierz*, [in:] T. Dubicki, A. Suchcitz, *Oficerowie wywiadu WP i PSZ w latach 1939-1945. Słownik biograficzny*, T. 2, Wydawnictwo LTW, Warszawa 2011, pp. 11-15.

⁴ J. Smoliński, *Polskie władze wojskowe na uchodźstwie 1939-1946*, Oficyna Wydawnicza RYTM, Warszawa 2017, p. 83, 88, 264 and 300.

⁵ PISM, For example see: A.XII.26-24 and A.XII.22-132.

⁶ The complete English and Polish texts of the 'Memorandum on Plan 'P', December 1943' can be found in the following files: PISM, A.XII.26-81 and The National Archive, Kew, London, (hereafter TNA), FO 371/39533 and WO 32/11090.

to a total of four, the armoured divisions increase to three, the infantry divisions increase to six, the airborne brigade expand into a division and the number of tank brigades increase to three. Total manpower of land forces in phase two was 263,300.⁷

Phase three of Plan 'P' was the return and expansion of the land forces from the North-West Europe and Mediterranean theatres. The resulting land force structure would be the initial peacetime design for the post-war Polish Army. Unchanged in the third phase was the one army and four corps headquarters, the three armoured and one airborne divisions and the three tank brigades now designated armoured brigades. The number of infantry divisions increased to nine in the third phase of the plan. So far all of the changes reflected continuity and an evolutionary development from the starting point of the wartime land forces of the Polish armed forces in the west. The new elements of the third phase of the plan included the addition of ten independent tank battalions and the creation of ten territorial divisions. The ten new territorial divisions were tied to specific military districts and presumably their recruitment of personnel would occur within the district's geographical boundary. What the operational role of the ten territorial divisions would be was not made clear in the plan, but they were to be fitted out with German equipment. The overall strength of Polish land forces on the completion of the third phase of the plan would be 473,350.⁸

Although the plan for the development of Polish land forces was realistic in building on the base of existing wartime Polish land forces, such a major expansion required a substantial amount of equipment. Even calculating the amount of material needed to equip the land forces in the post-war army proved a major challenge for the planners on the Polish General Staff. In order to calculate manpower and equipment needs with necessary precision, the Polish General Staff requested and received detailed tables of organization for all types of British Army formations and units.⁹

By utilizing a British military template, the General Staff was able to make detailed calculations in its force planning. The resulting assessment of equipment needs to complete the third phase of Plan 'P' presented a daunting list. This can be illustrated by examining the figures for several categories of equipment. The required numbers of artillery pieces of all types (anti-tank, anti-aircraft, self-propelled and towed artillery) totalled 6,910. The number of tanks and armoured cars amounted to 4,630. In the category of wheeled transport the number of lorries needed was approximately 47,000.¹⁰ Given the scale of equipment necessary to complete the third phase of the plan, meeting this requirement was going to be a major challenge.

⁷ The complete English and Polish texts of the 'Memorandum on Plan 'P', December 1943' can be found in the following files: PISM, A.XII.26-81 and The National Archive, Kew, London, (hereafter TNA), FO 371/39533 and WO 32/11090.

⁸ *Ibidem*.

⁹ *Ibidem*.

¹⁰ PISM, 'The Expansion of Polish Land Forces – 3rd Phase, Statements re. Weapons, Transport, Signal and Engineer Stores', 15 July 1944, A.XII.42-44.

Although the General Staff's plan was submitted to the War Office in December 1943, it was not until the last quarter of 1944 that a modified version of the first phase of Plan 'P' began to be implemented. Given the Polish dependency for military resources on the British side, the pace for moving the plan forward was inevitably going to be in the hands of the War Office. In military terms, however, the onset of Allied operations in France in June 1944 and the entry into combat of Polish formations by August created a need for Polish reinforcements. This gave a relevance to the plan for meeting operational requirements for manpower. In July 1944, in his memorandum to Field Marshall Alan Brooke, the Chief of the Imperial General Staff (CIGS), General Kazimierz Sosnkowski, the Polish Commander-in-Chief reaffirmed Polish commitment to Plan 'P' in its entirety.¹¹

BRITISH WAR OFFICE REACTION TO POLISH PLANS

The digesting of the Polish General Staff's Plan 'P' did not begin in earnest at the War Office until summer 1944. The initial assessment of the War Office saw the Polish plan as presenting two problems: one related to the wartime maintenance of Polish forces in the field and the other to the post-war future of Poland and its Army. The second problem was seen in the War Office as being beyond its authority in the analysis of General Sir Frank Simpson, Director of Military Operations (DMO):

*All three phases of the Polish Plan, and in particular Phases 2 and 3, are intimately bound up with the question of the future of Poland and of her armed forces, following the defeat of Germany. Our attitude must be governed by whatever policy His Majesty's Government may decide to adopt [...].*¹²

By August 1944, after the War Office had received Sosnkowski's memorandum, Simpson decided that the question of the development of the Polish Armed Forces was one that had to be submitted urgently to the Foreign Office for guidance.¹³ On 26 August 1944, a War Office official, G. W. Lambert, stressed in a lengthy letter to the Foreign Office that 'these proposals raise important political issues'.¹⁴

The Foreign Office was quick to dismiss the idea of Britain lending support to the second and third phases but left open the possibility of moving forward with the first phase of Plan 'P':

It is difficult to see why we should have had any responsibility of the third phase [...]. The manpower which is likely to fall available to the Polish authorities here will

¹¹ PISM, 'Memorandum Regarding Further Disposal of the Polish Armed Forces', 2 September 1944, A.XII.42-44.

¹² TNA, Minute by General Sir Frank Simpson, Director of Military Operations, 22 July 1944, WO 32/11090.

¹³ TNA, Minute by General Sir Frank Simpson, Director of Military Operations, 10 August 1944, WO 32/11090.

¹⁴ TNA, Letter G. W. Lambert to the Foreign Office, 26 August 1944, FO 371/39533.

*not do more than supply the reinforcements which the Polish Forces at present so badly need. In the circumstances, plans for further expansion are hypothetical and the War Office need not worry about them.*¹⁵

As early as 19 August 1944, the War Office made it clear to the General Staff that 'the expansion envisaged in phases two and three cannot be approved by the War Office without first obtaining approval for the policy aspect from the Foreign Office'.¹⁶ Both the Foreign Office and the War Office, however, did not see the recruitment of reinforcements for Polish formations already on operations as presenting major political difficulties.¹⁷ With the War Office in favour of allowing Polish recruitment to supply reinforcements, the next step was to get the concurrence of the headquarters of the Supreme Headquarters Allied Expeditionary Force (SHAEF) as recruitment in France would take place in SHAEF's zone of operations. With SHAEF's support, the War Office informed the General Staff in September 1944 that it was authorized to begin recruiting in France to a maximum of 10,000 men.¹⁸ Any hope of realizing the aims of Plan 'P' effectively ended in autumn 1944.

CONCLUSION: ASSESSING THE GENERAL STAFF'S VISION OF THE POST-WAR POLISH ARMY

It is easy to suggest that the General Staff's Plan 'P' stood no chance of realization with the trajectory of international politics on the future of Poland after 1943. Moreover, the War Office, in line with British Government policy, did not support any aspects of Plan 'P' other than those that met wartime operational needs. However such an assessment ignores the important military story contained in the General Staff's thinking on wartime development and eventual design for Polish land forces after the war. Polish General Staff's Plan 'P' provided an interesting snapshot of how the Polish Army might have looked had the Polish Government-in-Exile and its armed forces returned to post-war Poland.

Judging the efficacy of a plan that was not put into action is a difficult business. Some insight, however, can be drawn by comparing the projected force structure and strength at the completion of Plan 'P' with the peacetime manpower of the pre-war Polish Army on the eve of the war and the Polish Peoples' Army (*Ludowe Wojsko Polskie*) in the immediate post-war period. Plan 'P' created a post-war Polish Army consisting of twenty-three divisions and 473,350 men. Before mobilization, the pre-war Polish Army had 24 infantry divisions and a strength in manpower

¹⁵ TNA, Minute by Gatehouse, Foreign Office, 8 September 1944, FO 371/39533.

¹⁶ PISM, Letter Brigadier G.W. Way to Major General Bronislaw Regulski 19 August 1944, A.XII.22-132.

¹⁷ TNA, 'Memorandum by the Chief of the Imperial General Staff, Future of the Polish Forces', 26 September 1944, FO 371/39533.

¹⁸ PISM, Letter Brigadier G.W. Way to Major General Bronislaw Regulski 24 September 1944, A.XII.22-132.

of 250,900 in August 1939.¹⁹ While the number of divisions of the pre-war Polish Army roughly matched the number of divisions resulting from Plan 'P', the pre-war manpower levels were exceeded in Plan 'P' by about 220,000 men. This may be explained by the greater number of supporting units and other formations envisaged in Plan 'P', suggesting a more modern force structure than the interwar Army.

The Polish People's Army in May 1945 had a manpower strength of approximately 400,000 and fifteen infantry divisions.²⁰ This force level proved unsustainable in the grim conditions of the devastated Polish economy. By May 1947, the Polish Peoples' Army had had its manpower cut to just over 147,000.²¹ Comparisons between the Army resulting from Plan 'P' and the Polish Peoples' Army are difficult given the radically different British and Soviet templates shaping the force structure. What the Polish Peoples' Army example demonstrates is that the force levels of Plan 'P' were most likely unsustainable in post-war conditions. This last example points to the least credible military element in Plan 'P', concerning its material requirements. Plan 'P' unrealistically contained the assumption that British material assistance would be forthcoming or could be paid for out of Polish resources or that the Polish economy would be able to supply the necessary material.

The vision outlined in Plan 'P' aimed to create a balanced and well equipped force that built on the successful operational experience of the Polish Army in North-West Europe and Italy. The design of the force utilized the well understood British template and promised the construction of a modern and capable Army. In the end, however, the Plan 'P' was nothing more than an interesting planning exercise of the Polish General Staff in London. Wartime political constraints and limited post-war resources made the realization of Plan 'P' unfeasible.

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¹⁹ *Polskie Siły Zbrojne w drugiej wojnie światowej*, T. 1, *Kampania wrześniowa 1939*. Cz. 1, *Polityczne i wojskowe położenie Polski przed wojną*, Instytut Historyczny im. gen. Sikorskiego, Londyn 1951, p. 178 and 292.

²⁰ C. Grzelak, H. Stańczyk, S. Zwoliński, *Armia Berlinga i Żymierskiego. Wojsko Polskie na froncie wschodnim 1943-1945*, Wydawnictwo NERITON, Warszawa 2009, p. 125 and J. Sobiech, *Polityka władz partyjnych i państwowych wobec Ludowego Wojska Polskiego w latach 1949-1956*, Dom Wydawniczy ELIPSA, Warszawa 2017, p. 54.

²¹ J. Sobiech, *Polityka władz partyjnych...*, op. cit., p. 55.

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